

Title Socio-Cultural Analysis on Death Rites: Case Study of Ritual Death of Kempo People, West Manggarai, Flores-Indonesia

Data dan Informan Utama Wawancara

Data utama dari penelitian ini diperoleh melalui Wawancara terhadap beberapa Narasumber. Mereka adalah Gabriel Pampur, Stanislaus Tatan dan Simon Saidin. Gabriel Pampur adalah tokoh adat dan sering menjadi juru bicara adat baik dalam ritus kematian, perkawinan dan berbagai ritus adat lainnya. Stanislaus Tatan adalah mantan Kepala Desa Desat, dan Simon Saidin adalah informan yang sering menjadi juru bicara dalam berbagai ritus adat. Ketiga informan utama ini berasal dari Kempo, Kabupaten Manggarai Barat.

Data Observasi

Observasi terhadap ritus kematian dilakukan oleh penelitian terhadap ritus kematian bapak Rudolf Ruman (2012), Ibu Martina Namun (2022), Bapak Yakobus Baru (2012), Maria Magdalene Nggejang (2012 dan Maria Theresia Rosiyanti Ruman (2017).

Hasil Wawancara dan Observasi

Ritus kematian di wilayah Kempo Kabupaten Manggarai Barat dapat diringkas dalam tahapan-tahapan berikut:

1. Ritus Nggalak
2. Ritus Tokong Mbakung
3. Ritus Penguburan yang dimulai dari ritus Wego Waka, Penguburan,
4. Ritus Pasca Penguburan yang dimulai dari ritus Wentar Loce (malam keempat), ritus keti kembang (malam kedelapan)
5. Ritus Kelas.

Dokumentasi foto dan gambar yang dimuat dalam artikel:

Foto: Ritus angkos setelah penguburan

Ritus Keti Kembang

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